

Synthesis and biological activity of 3H-1,5-benzodiazepine derivatives

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Abstract : Acylation of 5-(2-ethoxyphenyl)-1-methyl-3-propyl-1,6-dihydro-7H-pyrazolo[4,3-d]pyrimidin-7-one (1) with chloroacetyl chloride in the presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride affords 5-(5-chloroacetyl-2-ethoxy)pyrimidin-1-methyl-3-propyl-1,6-dihydro-7H-pyrazolo[4,3-d]pyrimidin-7-one (2). Compound 2 condensed with different dicarbonyl compound (3a-e) to obtain new dicarbonyl compound (4a-c) which treated with *o*-phenylenediamine (*o*-PDA) give biologically active 3H-1,5-benzodiazepines (5a-c). All the newly synthesized compounds are characterized by elemental analysis and spectral studies. The compounds (5a-c) have been screened for antimicrobial, antifungal and anthelmintic activities.

Keywords : 1,5-Benzodiazepines, 1,3-diketones/1,3-ketoesters, pyrimidin-7-one, *p*-toluenesulfonic acid.

Benzodiazepines have attracted attention as an important class of heterocyclic compounds in the field of drugs and pharmaceuticals. These compounds are widely used as anticonvulsant, antianxiety, analgesic, sedative, antidepressive, hypnotic agents¹ as well as anti-inflammatory agents². Other than their biological importance, benzodiazepines derivatives are also commercially used as dyes for acrylic fibres³. Moreover, 1,5-benzodiazepines derivatives are valuable synthons that can be used in preparation of other fused ring compounds such as triazolo-, oxadiazolo-, oxazino-, or furano-benzodiazepines⁴. Research in this area is still very active and is directed towards the synthesis of compounds with enhanced pharmacological activity. Generally, these compounds are synthesized by the condensation of *o*-phenylenediamines with α,β -unsaturated carbonyl compounds⁵, β -haloketones, or ketones⁶. A variety of reagents, such as BF₃-etherate, NaBH₄, polyphosphoric acid, or SiO₂, MgO/POCl₃, Yb(OTf)₃, Sc(OTf)₃, Al₂O₃/P₂O₅, or AcOH under microwave and in ionic liquids⁷ have been utilized for condensation reaction. Most recently, this condensation has also been reported to proceed in the presence of CAN, (bromodimethyl)sulfonium bromide, organic acids and AgNO₃⁸. However, all of these methods have problems drastic reaction conditions and also several side-reactions. Surface-mediated solid phase reaction are of growing interest⁹ because of their ease of execution and work-up, mild reaction conditions, rate of reaction, selectivity, high yields, lack of solvents and low cost in comparison with their homogeneous counter parts. We have efforts to explore the utility of surface-mediated

reaction¹⁰⁻¹². We report here a new method for the preparation of 1,5-benzodiazepine derivatives with β -diketones and β -ketoesters. It was found that a mixture of *p*-toluenesulfonic acid/SiO₂ under solvent-free conditions was capable of producing high yields of 1,5-benzodiazepines (5a-c) by condensation of *o*-phenylenediamine with dicarbonyl compounds (4a-e) under mild conditions in 90% yield.

We were interested to synthesis pyrazolo[4,3-d]pyrimidin-7-one containing 1,5-benzodiazepines due to importance of this class of compound which has recently found great use in medicinal chemistry. Substituted pyrazolopyrimidinones are potent and selective inhibitors of type 5 cyclic guanosine-3',5'-monophosphate phosphodiesterase (CGMP) PDE-5^{13,14} which have utility in the treatment of male erectile dysfunction (MED)¹⁵ and female sexual dysfunction (FSD). They also found use in the treatment of impotence, one of male sexual dysfunction with the reduced side effects¹⁶. Substituted pyrazolopyrimidinones are also useful as CNS stimulant, bronchodilator, cardiotoxic¹⁷, herbicide¹⁸ and antiviral¹⁹ agent.

Results and discussion

5-(2-Ethoxyphenyl)-1-methyl-3-propyl-1,6-dihydro-7H-pyrazolo[4,3-d]pyrimidin-7-one was acylated with chloroacetyl chloride in the presence of anhydrous AlCl₃. Acylated compound was condensed with different 1,3-diketones/1,3-ketoesters in the presence of sodium methoxide (Scheme 1). The newly synthesized 1,3-

diketones/1,3-ketoesters (**4a-e**) were condensed with *o*-phenylenediamine (*o*-PDA) in the presence of *p*-toluenesulfonic acid, to obtain 3*H*-1,5-benzodiazepines (**5a-e**).

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

Table 1

Entry	R ¹ (4)	R ² (4)	R ¹ (5)	R ² (5)	Yield of 4 (%)	Yield of 5 (%)
a	CH ₃	CH ₃	CH ₃	CH ₃	78.7	82.8
b	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	81.6	85
c	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	72.5	83
d	CH ₃	OC ₂ H ₅	CH ₃	-	71.5	81.3
e	OC ₂ H ₅	OC ₂ H ₅	-	-	81.2	89.4

Antimicrobial and anthelmintic activities of compounds (**5a-e**) :

The newly synthesized diazepine compounds have been screened for antibacterial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and antifungal activity against *Aspergillus niger* and *Candida albicans* by the cup-plate method^{20,21}. Ceftriaxone and Clotrimazole were used as standards for comparison of antibacterial and antifungal activities, respectively. The results indicate that these compounds were active against all the four organisms. The anthelmintic activity was carried out on earth worms *Pheritima posthuma*, by a technique as described by Bagavant *et al.*²³ with modification. Piperazine citrate was used as standard drug. The results of antimicrobial and anthelmintic activity are reported in Table 2. The compound **5c** exhibited antimicrobial and antifungal activities more than the standard drug but compounds **5d** and **5e** showed significant anthelmintic activity.

Experimental

All the melting points were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. The IR spectra were recorded on a Nicolet-Magna-FT-IR-550 spectrometer in KBr pellets. ¹H NMR spectra were run on model DRX 300 at 300.13 MHz and 75 MHz respectively, in CDCl₃ solvent and TMS as an internal standard and mass spectra on a LCMS instrument. The purity of the newly synthesized compounds was checked by TLC. Satisfactory C, H, N analyses were obtained for all the compounds.

General procedure for the synthesis : 5-[(5-Chloroacetyl-2-ethoxy)phenyl]-1-methyl-3-propyl-1,6-dihydro-7*H*-pyrazolo[4,3-*d*]pyrimidin-7-one (**2**) :

To a solution of 5-(2-ethoxyphenyl)-1-methyl-3-propyl-1,6-dihydro-7*H*-pyrazolo[4,3-*d*]pyrimidin-7-one (3.12 g, 0.01 mol) in carbon tetrachloride (150 ml) was added anhydrous aluminium chloride (3.50 g, 0.03 mol) with stirring. Chloroacetyl chloride (7.9 ml, 0.1 mol) was added dropwise at such a rate that the temperature was maintained below 5 °C. After refluxing for four hours, the mixture was poured into 1 *M* hydrochloric acid (200 ml) and extracted with CH₂Cl₂. The organic layer was washed with saturated NaHCO₃. To the water layer was added hydrochloric acid until the solution showed neutral and then extracted with CH₂Cl₂. The combined organic layer were dried (MgSO₄) and concentrated *in vacuo*. A solid compound was obtained which was crystallized from benzene. Purity of the compound was checked with TLC using 7 : 2 : 1 (benzene : ethanol : ammonia) upper layer as mobile phase (m.p. 193 °C, yield 3.9 g, 78%).

Table 2. Antimicrobial and anthelmintic activities of compounds (5a-e)

Compd.	Antibacterial activity zone of inhibition (in mm)		Antifungal activity zone of inhibition (in mm)		Anthelmintic activity (in min)	
	<i>A. aureus</i>	<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>	Paralysis	Death
5a	12	11	17	16	91	96
5b	9	10	15	19	92	114
5c	21	22	23	29	101	117
5d	13	13	14	12	102	124
5e	15	10	12	18	103	125
Std.	24	26	22	24	100	125

General procedure for the synthesis : 5-[2-Ethoxy-5-(1,3-dimethyl/1,3-diphenyl/1-phenyl-3-methyl-1,3-ethoxypropane-1,3-dione-2-acetyl)phenyl]-1-methyl-3-propyl-1,6-dihydro-7H-pyrazolo[4,3-d]pyrimidin-7-one (4a-e) :

Sodium methoxide (0.54 g, 0.01 mol) and 1,3-diketones/1,3-ketoesters (0.01 mol) were placed in a dry round bottom flask without any solvent and stirred for one hour with a magnetic stirrer at a temperature of 50 °C, to obtain the sodium salt of 1,3-diketones/1,3-ketoesters. The acetyl chloride derivative (2) (3.885 g, 0.01 mol) was added followed by sufficient dry toluene as solvent to effect proper stirring of the reaction mass. The reaction mixture was heated for eighteen hours at 80 °C with stirring. The progress of the reaction was monitored with TLC. After the reaction was complete, the reaction mixture was cooled and toluene was removed under reduced pressure. The reaction mixture was extracted with chloroform (4 × 50 ml). The chloroform layer was washed with water and dried with anhydrous sodium sulphate. Chloroform was evaporated to get solid compound. The crude residue was purified through column chromatography. It was crystallized with chloroform and ethyl acetate. Purity of the compound was checked through TLC using 7 : 2 : 1 (benzene : ethanol : ammonia) upper layer as mobile phase (yield 71.5–81.6%).

Synthesis of 3H-1,5-benzodiazepines (5a-e) : General procedure :

1,3-Diketones/1,3-ketoesters (4a-e) (0.01 mol) and *p*-toluenesulfonic acid/SiO₂ (prepared by adding *p*-toluenesulfonic acid (2 g) and silica gel (2 g) in acetone, stirred for 0.5 h on magnetic stirrer and then acetone was removed by vacuum) mixed in mortar 10 min. To the aforesaid mixture taken in conical flask *o*-phenylenediamine (0.01 mol) was added, heated on water bath at 60 °C for 30 min. The reaction mixture was washed

with dichloromethane (200 mL), dried over (Na₂SO₄), and the solvent was evaporated to give the crude products. The crude products washed with ether to remove unreacted dicarbonyl compounds. The crude product was recrystallized from pet ether : ethyl acetate (1 : 1). Purity of the compound was checked through TLC using 7 : 2 : 1 (benzene : ethanol : ammonia) upper layer as mobile phase.

Spectral data :

5-[2-Ethoxy-5-(2,4-dimethyl-3H-1,5-benzodiazepine-3-acetyl)-phenyl]-1-methyl-3-propyl-1,6-dihydro-7H-pyrazolo[4,3-d]pyrimidin-7-one (5a) : Crystalline solid, m.p. 174 °C, yield 82.8%; IR (KBr) : 3320, 3130, 3050, 2915, 1730, 1600, 1245, 1030 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 1.02 (3H, t, *J* 7.97 Hz), 1.55–1.60 (2H, m), 1.64 (3H, t, *J* 6.95 Hz), 2.50 (6H, s), 2.65 (2H, t, *J* 7.58 Hz), 3.23 (2H, d, *J* 7.79 Hz), 3.80 (3H, s), 4.42 (2H, q, *J* 8.05 Hz), 5.25 (1H, t, *J* 7.85 Hz), 7.27–8.45 (7H, m), 8.73 (1H, s); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 160.65, 149.93, 132.50–126.34, 75.37, 67.88, 53.26, 40.39, 15.87, 14.72; (Found : C, 67.98; H, 6.06; N, 15.97. Calcd. for C₃₀H₃₂N₆O₃ : C, 68.70; H, 6.10; N, 16.03%); LCMS : 525 (M+H⁺).

5-[2-Ethoxy-5-(2,4-diphenyl-3H-1,5-benzodiazepine-3-acetyl)phenyl]-1-methyl-3-propyl-1,6-dihydro-7H-pyrazolo[4,3-d]pyrimidin-7-one (5b) : m.p. 195 °C, yield 85%; IR (KBr) : 3310, 3100, 3020, 2960, 1710, 1605, 1250, 1025 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 1.02 (3H, t, *J* 7.93 Hz), 1.55–1.60 (2H, m), 1.57 (3H, t, *J* 7.56 Hz), 2.65 (2H, t, *J* 8.51 Hz), 3.44 (2H, d, *J* 7.48 Hz), 3.80 (3H, s), 4.42 (2H, q, *J* 7.58 Hz), 5.25 (1H, t, *J* 8.02 Hz), 7.36–8.40 (14H, m), 8.80 (3H, s); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 160.64, 149.95, 133.63–126.32, 75.37, 67.84, 53.25, 40.34, 15.82, 14.74; (Found : C, 71.57; H, 5.20; N, 12.75. Calcd. for C₄₀H₃₆N₆O₄ : C, 72.29; H, 5.42; N, 12.80%); LCMS : 665 (M+H⁺).

5-[2-Ethoxy-5-(1-phenyl-4-methyl-3H-1,5-benzodiazepine-3-acetyl)phenyl]-1-methyl-3-propyl-1,6-dihydro-7H-pyrazolo[4,3-d]pyrimidin-7-one (**5c**): m.p. 230 °C, yield 83%; IR (KBr): 3325, 3130, 3050, 2930, 1656, 1610, 1245, 1020 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 1.02 (3H, t, J 7.55 Hz), 1.55–1.60 (2H, m), 1.57 (3H, t, J 7.98 Hz), 2.65 (2H, t, J 8.11 Hz), 4.42 (2H, q, J 7.85 Hz), 3.43 (2H, d, J 7.56 Hz), 3.80 (3H, s), 5.25 (1H, t, J 8.58 Hz), 7.36–8.40 (13H, m), 8.70 (1H, s); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 164.6, 160.69, 134.05–126.24, 65.11, 33.74, 24.95, 23.39, 15.65, 13.67; (Found: C, 71.53; H, 5.50; N, 14.21. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{35}\text{H}_{34}\text{N}_6\text{O}_3$: C, 71.67; H, 5.80; N, 14.33%); LCMS: 526 (M+H⁺).

5-[2-Ethoxy-5-(4-methyl-1,3-dihydro-3H-1,5-benzodiazepine-2-one-3-acetyl)phenyl]-1-methyl-3-propyl-1,6-dihydro-7H-pyrazolo[4,3-d]pyrimidin-7-one (**5d**): m.p. 165 °C, yield 81.3%; IR (KBr): 3300, 3120, 3030, 2950, 1720, 1580, 1260, 1020 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 1.02 (3H, t, J 7.45 Hz), 1.55–1.62 (2H, m), 1.57 (3H, t, J 7.47 Hz), 2.65 (3H, t, J 7.48 Hz), 2.40 (3H, s), 3.25 (2H, d, J 8.45 Hz), 3.80 (3H, s), 4.42 (2H, q, J 7.95 Hz), 5.30 (1H, t, J 8.06 Hz), 7.25–8.60 (7H, m), 8.75 (2H, s); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 157.23, 149.95, 132.23–128.30, 75.32, 68.39, 54.34, 40.37, 29.50, 15.84, 14.67; (Found: C, 66.54; H, 5.74; N, 16.03. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{29}\text{N}_6\text{O}_4$: C, 65.83; H, 5.80; N, 16.14%); LCMS: 587 (M+H⁺).

5-[2-Ethoxy-5-(1,5-dihydro-3H-1,5-benzodiazepine-2,4-dione-3-acetyl)phenyl]-1-methyl-3-propyl-1,6-dihydro-7H-pyrazolo[4,3-d]pyrimidin-7-one (**5e**): m.p. 174 °C, yield 89.4%; IR (KBr): 3300, 3120, 3060, 2930, 1720, 1600, 1240, 1030 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 1.02 (3H, t, J 7.48 Hz), 1.55–1.61 (2H, m), 1.62 (3H, t, J 7.32 Hz), 2.65 (2H, t, J 8.58 Hz), 3.25 (2H, d, J 7.15 Hz), 3.80 (3H, s), 4.44 (2H, q, J 8.23 Hz), 5.30 (1H, t, J 7.86 Hz), 7.3–8.8 (7H, m), 8.75 (3H, s); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 165.51, 157.12, 149.84, 132.34–126.67, 75.35, 68.38, 54.88, 40.34, 15.87, 14.67; (Found: C, 63.18; H, 5.03; N, 16.28. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_6\text{O}_5$: C, 62.93; H, 5.13; N, 16.29%); LCMS: 527 (M+H⁺).

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